

Studies on Cut-Protective Performance of Composites Yarn Based Knitted UHMWPE Textiles in Real-world Industrial Applications

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ABSTRACT

The safety of workers in hazardous environments depends on advanced protective textiles capable of withstanding various real-world challenges, especially in automotive, glass, aerospace, mining, construction, and food industries where cut hazards are prevalent. Developing flexible, high-performance protective textiles is essential to meet these needs. Ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) is widely utilized in cut-protective textiles for its exceptional strength and durability. This study investigates the cut-performance of stainless-steel and glass fibers reinforced UHMWPE knitted fabrics under real-world industrial conditions, focusing on the impact of varying cutting angles, outdoor environments, and thermal exposure on their cut-protective efficacy in industrial and occupational settings. Reinforcement significantly affects cut-performance, with stainless-steel reinforced UHMWPE fabric (13SU) exhibited the highest tear strength (lengthwise-313.1 N, widthwise-405.8 N) and abrasion resistance (withstanding up to 800 rubbing cycles), providing superior cut-protection with cut force of 32.43 N at a 90° cutting angle. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and scanning electron microscope (SEM) characterizations revealed UHMWPE's sensitivity to thermal effects, with a significant decrease in crystallinity after exposure to radiant heat flux of 20 kW/m² at fabric surface, leading to diminished cut-performance. Environmental durability assessments showed degradation due to galvanic corrosion, forming ketone (C=O) and hydroxyl (O-H) polar groups that altered the UHMWPE polymer structure and reduced peak intensity, as confirmed by Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. This study would be highly beneficial for industrial employees in choosing the right cut-protective fabrics based on their specific environments and working conditions.

Highlights

- Development of stainless-steel and glass fiber reinforced UHMWPE fabrics.
- TDM-100 is integrated with radiant heater to assess cut-performance under heat.
- Reinforced UHMWPE fabrics shows higher cut-performance than 100% UHMWPE fabric.
- Cut protection is highest at 90° cutting angle.
- Glass reinforced UHMWPE fabric offers better cut-protection under heat.

Keywords: UHMWPE, cut-resistance fabric, glass fibers, stainless-steel, crystallinity, composite yarns, radiant heat exposure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Occupational safety remains a critical concern worldwide, with millions of workers facing potential hazards in industries such as manufacturing, construction, and emergency services. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), over 317 million work-related injuries occur annually, and more than 320,000 people die, leading to significant human and economic costs. Among these, injuries from sharp objects and exposure to extreme environmental conditions are particularly common, underscoring the need for effective protective measures.¹ In response to these safety challenges, various protective clothing has been designed, such as cut-resistant gloves, bulletproof vests, stab-proof suits, and protective helmets.²⁻⁴ These advancements are intended to help the human body better withstand or even completely avoid injuries caused by sharp objects and other hazardous impacts.^{5, 6} However, traditional protective solutions such as leather garments, wire mesh steel, and steel gloves have faced several limitations, including discomfort, reduced dexterity, and inadequate protection.⁷ In contrast, modern protective textiles are developed using high-performance fibers such as ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene (UHMWPE),^{8, 9} aramids,¹⁰⁻¹² polyphenylene benzobisoxazole (PBO) fiber,^{13, 14} as well as inorganic fibers including, glass fibers,^{15, 16} carbon fibers,¹⁷ and basalt fibers¹⁸ exhibit excellent mechanical properties, and have proven to be an effective approach for preparing cut-/puncture resistant textile materials. These advanced materials offer superior protection without compromising on dexterity or comfort. Mayo and Wetzel¹⁹ studied the cut-resistance properties of both inorganic and organic high-performance single fibers and attributed their effectiveness to the fibers to their isotropic and anisotropic structures.¹⁹ Additionally, a U.S. patent titled ‘Criminology’ suggests using glass fiber as a cut-resistant material, highlighting its exceptional ability to protect against sharp objects like knives and cones.²⁰ In a comparative study, Tuba Alpyildiz²¹ developed a double-sided knitted fabric

using yarn wrapped with Kevlar 1414 fiber, which exhibited significantly higher cut-resistance than traditional weft-knitted fabrics.²¹ Javid et al.²² developed knitted gloves using a combination of core yarns like stainless-steel filament, Kevlar filament, staple spun Kevlar, and glass filament, with sheath yarns made of 100% viscose rayon, 50/50 polyester/viscose rayon blend. Their testing revealed that gloves utilizing dual-core yarns, especially those incorporating both filament and staple spun Kevlar, demonstrated superior performance in cut, tear, puncture, and abrasion resistance properties.²² Cut-resistance clothing is primarily produced using knitting and weaving techniques, with knitting being favored for its stretchability, flexibility, and lightweight properties.²³ Research by Flambard et al.²⁴ found that knitted structures made from high-performance fibers offer better energy absorption during impact, making them more effective for protective clothing than woven fabrics.^{24, 25}

Numerous studies have examined the mechanical properties of high-performance single fibers under various conditions, including tension at both high and low strain rates^{26, 27}, torsion^{28, 29}, and transverse compression.³⁰ When cutting a single fiber under tension, the fiber likely undergoes a combination of loading modes, which may include aspects of these mechanisms along with in-plane shear.³¹⁻³⁶ UHMWPE fiber has a molecular weight exceeding one million³⁷, it demonstrates significantly higher strength and cutting resistance than other fibers, making it notably difficult to cut. This exceptional durability has led to the extensive use of UHMWPE-based knitted cut-resistant protective gear, including gloves, vests, socks, and t-shirts, across various global industries to protect workers. The cut performance of these fabrics is influenced by several factors, such as outdoor environmental conditions, cutting angles, the type of reinforcement used in the core of the UHMWPE yarn, and thermal exposure. However, the impact of these factors, particularly the influence of heat, has not been previously critically analyzed. UHMWPE fibers are especially sensitive to temperature due to their relatively low melting point, below 150 °C,^{38, 39} which can significantly affect their cut performance.

In this study, cut-resistant knitted fabrics were produced on 13-gauge gloves knitting machine using UHMWPE core-spun composite yarn reinforced with stainless-steel and glass fibers. The effects of various factors, including core reinforcement (stainless-steel and glass fibers), outdoor environmental exposure (up to 90 days), different cutting angles (0°, 45°, 90°), and radiant heat exposure (heat flux density of 20 kW/m² at mandrel), on the mechanical and cut-resistant properties were critically analyzed. To assess the impact of radiant heat on cut performance, the cut-resistant testing instrument, a tomodynamometer, was integrated with an external radiant heat exposure lamp, enabling the cut performance evaluation of the developed

samples under controlled heat conditions. This study offers critical findings that can help employees in various industries by guiding the selection of more durable and effective cut-resistant protective gear, particularly in environments with extreme conditions such as high temperatures and outdoor exposure.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials

The commercially available high-performance yarns such as 100% UHMWPE, as well as stainless-steel and glass-reinforced UHMWPE core spun composite yarns were directly sourced from HPT Pvt Ltd in Sonipat, Haryana, India. The core spun composite yarns were produced by using ring spinning process, wherein UHMWPE fibers as sheath layer and polyester fibers as intermediate layer were wrapped out with reinforced materials such as stainless-steel and glass fibres, as shown in **Figure 1 a-c**. The inclusion of intermediate layer significantly enhances the stability of the resulting yarn, preventing the core materials from coming out. The physical properties of sourced yarns are illustrated in **Table 1**.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of yarn structural configuration and cross-sectional SEM images of **(a, a1)** 100% UHMWPE yarn, **(b, b1)** stainless-steel reinforced UHMWPE composite yarn, **(c, c1)** glass fiber reinforced UHMWPE composite yarn.

Table 1. Physical properties of 100% UHMWPE and core spun composite yarns

Sr. No.	Yarn type	Sheath layer		Intermediate layer		Core	
		Fiber	Fineness (Denier)	Fiber	Fineness (Denier)	Fiber	Fineness (Denier)
1	100% UHMWPE	UHMWPE	800	-	-	-	-
2	Stainless-steel/UHMWPE	UHMWPE	400	Polyester	150	Stainless-steel	200
3	Glass Fibers/UHMWPE	UHMWPE	400	Polyester	150	Glass fiber	200

Table 2. Mechanical properties of 100% UHMWPE and core spun composite yarns

Yarn specifications	100 % UHMWPE	Stainless steel/UHMWPE	Glass/UHMWPE
Linear density (tex)	89±5	90±5	90±5
Breaking load (N)	80.4	99.5	96.8
Tenacity (gf/den)	11.3	12.6	12.3
Young modulus (gf/den)	282.1	301.5	351.5
Diameter (mm)	0.82	0.85	0.85

2.2 Fabrication of cut resistance samples

The knitted cut-resistance fabrics in form of gloves were prepared on 13-gauge computerized gloves knitting machine (SHIMA SEIKI SFG-I). These glove samples are produced using the tubular knitting technology that creates a dual-layer structure, with each layer utilizing a single jersey pattern, resulting in the formation of a hollow space (pocket) between the layers (in Finger part and palm part), as shown in **Figure 2 b**. The gloves samples made from 100% UHMWPE, glass fibers-reinforced UHMWPE, and stainless-steel fibers-reinforced UHMWPE composite yarns are designated as 13U, 13GU, and 13SU, respectively. The microscopic image of the 13SU gloves is depicted in **Figure 2 d**.

Figure 2. Fabrication of cut resistance knitted gloves: **(a)** arrangement of loops in the needle bed on gloves knitting machine; **(b)** schematic representation of loops arrangement on needle bed during formation of finger part and palm part of the glove; **(c)** developed glove samples; **(d)** microscopic image of 13SU glove sample.

2.3 Characterization and measurement techniques

The physical characteristics of the single jersey knitted fabric, such as thickness and GSM (grams per square meter), were measured following ASTM standards D177 and D3776, respectively. The mechanical properties of the 100% UHMWPE and core-spun composite UHMWPE yarns were determined according to ASTM D2256-02. The cut resistance of all samples was evaluated using a tomodynamometer (TDM-100) cut testing instrument. Before testing, the samples were conditioned for 24 hours in a controlled environment with a temperature of 20 ± 2 °C and a relative humidity of $65 \pm 4\%$ as per standard procedures.

2.3.1 Measurement of cut-resistance properties

The cut-resistance properties of all samples were measured according to standard ISO 13997 using instrument tomodynamometer (TDM-100), as shown in **Figure 3 a**. According to this test method, sample with size of 7x7 cm fixed on mandrel by mounting tape (**Figure 3 b**), and the force required for a blade to cut the samples after a sliding displacement of 20 mm at constant speed of 2.5 mm/sec is measured. Each sample were cut 15 times under varying loads, such as the cut distances ranging from 5 mm to 15 mm, 15 mm to 30 mm, and 30 mm to 50

mm. Throughout each test, the applied loads and corresponding cut distances were collected, then corrected cut through distances (CCTD) were calculated by following **Equation 1**.

$$\text{Corrected cut through distance (CCTD)} = \frac{20}{d_o} \times d \quad (1)$$

Where d_o represents the calibration cut-through distance, calculated as the average distance from five blades on a chloroprene standard sample, and d is the cut distance measured for the test sample.

Using this data, an optimal regression line fitting curve of CCTD and load (N) was plotted (**Figure 3 c**). The load corresponding to CCTD of 20 mm was considered as characteristic cut protection force.

Figure 3. (a) TDM-100 cut testing instrument (b) schematic view of performing cut testing (c) plot of corrected cut through distance (CCTD) verses applied load and resulting cutting load at 20-mm CCTD.

2.3.2 Testing setup for cut performance under radiant heat exposure

The influence of radiant heat exposure on cut performance was assessed by radiant heat lamp based tomodynamometer (**Figure 4**). The heat flux was calibrated by adjusting the distance between the radiant heat lamp and the mandrel of the TDM-100. It was determined that at a distance of 28.5 cm, the heat flux density at the mandrel reached 20 kW/m^2 . This specific heat flux was chosen based on the ISO-11612 standard, "Protective clothing – Clothing to protect against heat and flame – Minimum performance requirements," which recommends exposing protective fabrics to a radiant heat source of 20 kW/m^2 for a specified duration to evaluate their internal structure and shall meet at least performance Level C1. If the temperature rise within the fabric remains below a certain threshold, the material is deemed suitable for use in high-

heat environments. The heat flux from the radiant source can be adjusted depending on the intended application. After exposing the samples to radiant heat for 5 minutes, the lamp was turned off, and the cut resistance properties was measured as discussed in section 2.3.1.

Figure 4. TDM-100 integrated with radiant heat exposure lamp.

2.3.3 Mechanical properties evaluation

The mechanical properties of all samples, including tear resistance, puncture resistance, and abrasion resistance, were evaluated according to the EN 388:2016 standard. Tear and puncture resistance tests were conducted using an electronic universal testing machine (**Supporting Figure S1**), while abrasion resistance was measured with a Martindale abrasion tester, as shown in **Supporting Figure S3**. For the tear resistance test, samples were prepared by making a 50 mm longitudinal incision on one side of 100×50 mm fabric strips, creating a "pants" shape (**Supporting Figure S2**). The grips of the mechanical testing frame were clamped onto the two "legs" of each sample, which were then pulled apart at a constant speed of 100 mm/min. Load-extension data were continuously recorded to determine the maximum force that the fabric could withstand before tearing. In the puncture resistance test, samples were cut into 40 mm diameter circles, and a needle was allowed to move downwards at a constant speed of 100 mm/min until it fully penetrated the fabric. The force required to achieve full penetration was recorded as the puncture load. For the abrasion resistance test, the samples with a diameter of

38 mm were cut from each fabric sample. Each sample was tested against a standard abradant fabric (180-grit, Klingspor PL31B) under a pressure of 9 kPa, and specimens were subjected to abrasion cycles until the hole formation observed.

2.3.4 Durability assessment in open environmental conditions

The durability evaluation of cut resistance fabrics under open environmental conditions is essential because these fabrics are often exposed to factors like sunlight, moisture, and temperature fluctuations in real-world use. Over time, external elements may affect mechanical and cut-resistant properties of the fabrics. This evaluation helps ensure that the fabrics maintain their protective performance over time, providing reliable safety for users. Samples of 13U, 13SU, and 13GU fabrics were exposed to outdoor conditions for 90 days, as depicted in **Figure 5**. The mechanical properties and cut performance of these fabrics were systematically assessed at 30 days intervals to analyse any changes in their durability and effectiveness throughout the exposure period.

Figure 5. Investigation of environmental effect on the performance of 13U, 13GU, and 13SU samples.

2.3.5 Thermal analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was done using a Q2000V24.11 Build 124 DSC analyzer, with continuous nitrogen purging throughout the process. UHMWPE/Polyester blended samples were finely granulated (3–5 mg) and sealed in aluminium pans. The samples first underwent a heating cycle from the temperature of 0 °C to 350 °C at a rate of 10°C/min.

This was followed by rapid cooling (quenching) to 0 °C, where the samples were held for 8 minutes to achieve equilibrium. The melting temperature (T_m) and crystallization temperature (T_c) were identified as the inflection point in the DSC thermograms.

2.3.6 Chemical structure analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to analyze the effects of environmental conditions on the structure of UHMWPE polymer chains and their molecular interactions. The analysis was conducted using a Nicolet iS50 spectrophotometer, equipped with an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode featuring a zinc selenide crystal. Spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , after performing 64 scans to ensure detailed and accurate results.

2.3.7 X-ray diffraction

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed using an XPert Pro PANalytical X-ray diffractometer to assess the crystallinity percentage and the impact of radiant heat exposure on the crystal planes within the fabric structures. The samples were scanned over a diffraction angle range of 2θ from 0° to 40°, with a scanning speed of 4°/min and a step size of 0.02°. The XRD instrument operated under conditions of 40 keV and 40 mA.

2.3.8 Surface morphology characterization

The microscopic images and surface morphology of fabric structures subjected to cut tests under radiant heat exposure and different cutting angles were examined using an optical microscope and a Zeiss EVO 18 scanning electron microscope (SEM). SEM imaging was conducted in a vacuum environment with an acceleration voltage of 20 kV.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The physical characteristics of the developed samples, such as course per inch (CPI), wales per inch (WPI), stitch density, loop length, fabric thickness, and areal density were assessed and are detailed in **Table 3**. The findings indicate that after reinforcement of stainless-steel and glass fibers into the core, there was no significant increase in the areal density of any of the samples, indicating it is suitable for use in comfortable protective clothing. There are several factors that can influence the cut resistance properties, including core reinforcement, cutting angles, exposure to outdoor environmental conditions, and radiant heat exposure. These factors

have been studied in next subsection to evaluate their effects on fabric performance and durability.

Table 3. Physical characteristics of developed fabric samples

Properties	13U	13GU	13SU
CPI/WPI	22/15	24/16	26/15
Loop length (mm)	6.5	5.8	5.7
Stitch density (loops/inch ²)	330	384	390
Tightness factor	13.4	16.2	15.9
Areal density (g/m ²)	305 ± 5	355 ± 5	320 ± 5
Thickness (mm)	0.87	0.95	0.93

3.1 Effect of core reinforcement

3.1.1 Tear resistance properties

Tear strength of samples was determined in lengthwise and widthwise direction using ZWICK instrument with gauge length of 40 mm and at a constant speed of 100 mm/min. **Figure 6 a-c** illustrates the force-extension curves of all samples, demonstrating that as the tearing force were applied to the fabric, it increased exponentially until fabric tear. This is due to as the force increase, the yarns bunches together, which requires high force to stretch and break them. At a higher force, the curve begins to oscillate because of the fabric starts to tear one yarn at a time until at a higher force all jam up yarns ruptures at once. And it was observed from the curves that the amplitude of the oscillations in widthwise direction larger than lengthwise direction across all samples. This implies that the material in widthwise direction experiences more significant slipping or rearrangement events under stress, resulting in higher tear strength in the width-wise direction across all samples compared to lengthwise direction. (**Figure 6 d**) This phenomenon can also be attributed to the mechanics of tear propagation in weft knitted structures. When initiating a tear in the lengthwise direction of the fabric, the strain experienced in the fabric's course direction allows for greater mobility of yarn. This is attributed to higher extensibility of single jersey knitted structures in the fabric's course direction compared to the wales direction. Consequently, as the tear progresses in the lengthwise direction, the stress in

the fabric's wales direction, which is inherently less extensible, acts to restrict the mobility of the yarns. This restriction occurs because the loop in the wale or needle way has tied at the head and at the leg of the loop, resulting in minimal elongation when force is applied. As a result, a higher force is required to tear the fabric in the widthwise direction.

Figure 6 d shows that 13SU fabric highest tear strength in length wise and widthwise direction, which is 313.1 N and 405.8 N, compared to 13GU (lengthwise-224.9 N, widthwise-326.5 N) and 13U (lengthwise-212.8 N, widthwise-275.6 N) fabric, it is due to higher the tenacity (12.6 gf/den) and young modulus (301.5 gf/den) of stainless-steel reinforced yarn, as shown in **Table 2**. Basically, in a core-sheath type of yarn, the core is expected to bear the load. Moreover, slippage occurs in the composites yarn between core and sheath fibers during the breaking process and thus core material has a great contribution to the tensile load sharing. So, stronger the core material higher will be the yarn and fabric tensile strength. As a result, stainless-steel and glass fibers reinforced UHMWPE yarn shows higher tensile strength compared to 100% UHMWPE staple spun yarn.

Figure 6. Load-extension curves of (a) 13U, (b) 13GU, and (c) 13SU fabrics in lengthwise and widthwise directions. (d) Comparison of breaking force required for the samples.

3.1.2 Puncture and abrasion resistance properties

All fabric samples were fixed for quasi-static puncture resistance experiments (**Figure 7 a**), and the results showed that the reinforced fabric samples (13SU and 13GU) had significant differences in their mechanical behaviour under stress compared to 13U fabric. The maximum puncture load was highest for the 13GU fabric at 111.97 N, which is 1.25 times higher than that of the 13U fabric (89.47 N), followed by 96.25 N for the 13SU fabric (**Figure 7 f**). This variation in puncture resistance is largely due to the reinforcing materials (glass fibers and stainless-steel fibers) used in the 13GU and 13SU fabrics, which significantly enhance their ability to resist puncture compared to the pure UHMWPE fabric. The presence of glass fibers in 13GU and stainless-steel in 13SU increases the energy required to penetrate the fabrics, as these reinforcements effectively distribute the stress across a larger area and absorb more energy before failure. Additionally, the 13GU fabric exhibited excellent energy dissipation

performance throughout the probe puncture phases I, II, III, and IV (**Figure 7 e**), indicating the excellent synergistic toughening properties. Friction and fiber slipping also play crucial roles in determining puncture resistance. The reinforced 13SU and 13GU fabrics create higher frictional resistance against the puncturing probe, which prevents easy fiber movement and slipping, thereby requiring more force for penetration. In contrast, the 13U fabric, lacking such reinforcements, has lower inter-fiber friction, allowing the fibers to slip more easily around the puncture point, which results in lower puncture resistance. Additionally, the strong bonding between UHMWPE fibers and the reinforcing materials in 13GU and 13SU contributes to their higher puncture resistance. Glass fibers, being stiffer and having higher hardness than stainless-steel,⁴⁰ create a rigid and well-bonded structure in 13GU, leading to the highest puncture load observed. Although stainless-steel in 13SU also enhances bonding and strength, the metal's relative flexibility compared to glass results in a slightly lower puncture load. The structural arrangement of fibers in the 13SU and 13GU fabrics, particularly the larger gaps between them, allows for more significant deformation and stretching around the puncture site before complete penetration. This is evident in the larger probe punctured openings observed in the 13GU and 13SU fabrics (**Figure 7 c-d**), whereas the 13U fabric, with smaller gaps between fibers (**Figure 7 b**), exhibits a lesser localized deformation and a pronounced “cross window” effect but with lower overall puncture resistance.

Figure 7. (a) Schematic representation of quasi-static puncture resistance test. Probe punctured deformation of (b) 13U, (c) 13SU, and (d) 13GU fabric samples. (e) Schematic diagram of the probe puncture process: **I** the puncture probe head just touched the fabric; **II** the puncture probe head started to compress the fabric; **III** the PN part of the puncture probe head pierced the fabric; **IV** the NM part of the puncture probe head entered the fabric completely. (f) Comparison of puncture force of the samples.

The abrasion resistance testing of 13U, 13SU, and 13GU fabrics was performed on Martindale abrasion tester, employing a Lissajous motion and rubbing against 180-grit Klingspor PL31B sandpaper under a pressure of 9 kPa. Abrasion resistance properties is generally influenced by factors such as, fabric thickness, GSM, tensile strength, and the type of the fibers used. The results shows that the 13SU fabric, reinforced with stainless-steel, exhibited superior abrasion resistance, with a hole forming at its surface after 800 cycles of rubbing. In contrast, the 13GU fabric, reinforced with glass fibers, showed a hole formation after 450 cycles, and the 13U fabric, composed of 100% UHMWPE, developed a hole after 350 cycles. (**Figure 8**)

The superior performance of 13SU can be attributed to the inherent properties of stainless-steel, which provide excellent resistance to abrasive forces, contributing to the fabric's high tensile strength of 804 N. The higher tensile strength enhances the fabric's ability to withstand repeated friction without significant material degradation. Additionally, 13SU recorded an extensibility of 72.3 mm/110.3 mm in lengthwise/widthwise direction before break (**Figure 10 j**), indicating a high ability to stretch under load, which plays a crucial role in its abrasion resistance. When the 13SU fabric comes into contact with the 180-grit Klingspor PL31B abrasive surface, its high extensibility allows it to deform and distribute the applied forces more evenly across the contact area. This results in a loose gripping contact with the abradant, reducing the localized stress and minimizing the damage, which in turn delays the onset of hole formation. In comparison, the 13GU fabric, while still exhibiting improved abrasion resistance over 13U, performed less favourably than 13SU due to the brittle nature of glass fibers. The tensile strength of 13GU was recorded at 569 N (lesser than 13SU), is compromised by the brittleness of glass fibers under abrasive conditions. When subjected to friction, the stiffness of the glass fibers causes a rigid response, and their brittle nature leads to breakage and dislodgement from the yarn structure, resulting in significant damage to the fabric surface and earlier hole formation. Additionally, the 13GU fabric has an extensibility of 61.6 mm/107.5 mm in the lengthwise/widthwise direction before breaking, which is lower than that of 13SU. This lower extensibility means the fabric cannot absorb and distribute abrasive forces as effectively, leading to greater damage under the same conditions. The 13U fabric, with a tensile strength of 264 N and an extensibility of 58.7 mm/99.45 mm in lengthwise/widthwise directions, exhibits the least resistance to abrasion. Its lower extensibility means that when it is subjected to frictional forces, the fabric is less able to deform and dissipate the energy generated by the abrasion. This results in a more concentrated stress on the contact area, leading to faster wear and earlier hole formation. The lack of reinforcing materials in 13U also results in a thinner fabric structure (0.835 mm) compared to 13GU (0.95 mm) and 13SU (0.93 mm), which further reduces its ability to resist abrasive forces.

Figure 8. Optical microscopic images of the samples before and after abrasion testing until hole formation

3.1.3 Cut resistance properties

The procedure described in the **section 2.3.1** was used to evaluate the cut protection level of all fabrics. Regression curves were plotted for each sample, and the corrected cut-through distances at 20 mm were calculated from these curves to quantitatively evaluate the cut performance. As seen in **Figure 9 b-c**, the analysis revealed that cut performance of reinforced UHMWPE yarn fabrics (13SU and 13GU), was significantly superior to that of 100% UHMWPE fabrics (13U). Among the tested samples, the 13SU fabric exhibited the highest cut resistance properties, which can be thoroughly explained by XRD analysis of samples. As shown in **Figure 9 a**, the XRD peaks occurring at 21.5° and 23.9° , that are characteristic of the UHMWPE polymer. The peak intensities vary among the different fabrics, with the highest intensity observed in 13SU, followed by 13GU, and then 13U. The higher peak intensity in 13SU indicates a greater degree of crystallinity and molecular order, correlating with its superior mechanical properties and cut resistance. This increased crystallinity in 13SU, at 52.48%, can be attributed to the effective nucleating action of the stainless-steel fibers, which facilitate a more ordered alignment of polymer chains during the crystallization process. The

peak intensity in 13GU, while still higher than in 13U, reflects its relatively lower crystallinity at 51.75%, resulting in less mechanical strength compared to 13SU. The 13U fabric, with the lowest crystallinity at 48.37%, exhibits the weakest performance, as indicated by its lower peak intensity. These findings are further supported by tensile strength data, which shows that 13SU has the highest tensile strength at 804 N, followed by 13GU at 569 N, and 13U at 264 N, as discussed earlier. The enhanced tensile strength in 13SU is due to the strong interaction between the stainless-steel reinforcement and the UHMWPE fibers, enabling more effective load transfer and contributing to the material's overall mechanical strength. In comparison, glass fibers in 13GU, though beneficial, are more brittle and have a lower bonding efficiency with the UHMWPE matrix, resulting in slightly lower tensile strength.

The molecular structure of UHMWPE, primarily composed of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ units, is characterized by strong sigma (σ) bonds. However, these chains lack rigidity due to the absence of additional functional groups that could restrict chain mobility. The introduction of reinforcement materials alters this molecular structure by increasing crystallinity and improving mechanical properties. In 13SU, stainless-steel creates stronger van der Waals forces and electron cloud interactions between the polymer chains and the reinforcement material, contributing to a more stable and ordered structure that is better able to resist cutting forces. In contrast, 13GU, reinforced with glass fibers, has different interactions. Glass fibers are rigid and brittle, creating a composite with air pockets and weaker van der Waals forces compared to the metal-reinforced composite. This brittleness, along with the presence of air pockets, makes the material more susceptible to crack initiation and fracture under stress, reducing its cut resistance. During the cutting process, the behaviour of the fibers plays a crucial role. The stainless-steel in 13SU exhibits ductile cutting behaviour, deforming plastically before fracturing, which allows it to absorb more energy and resist cut-through more effectively. This ductility, combined with the strong bonding between the stainless-steel and the UHMWPE fibers, results in the highest cut resistance among the tested samples. In contrast, the lower friction coefficient of glass fibers, coupled with their brittle nature, results in a less effective resistance mechanism compared to 13SU.

Figure 9. (a) XRD curve of fabric samples. (b) The CCTD-load data and regression line of fabric samples. (c) Comparison of cutting load at 20-mm CCTD derived from CCTD vs load curve.

3.2 Effect of cutting angles

The cut performance of all samples including 13U, 13GU, and 13SU were examined at varying angles 0° , 45° , and 90° (**Figure 10 d-f**). At 0° (lengthwise direction), the cut forces for 13U, 13SU, and 13GU were 9.563 N, 22.609 N, and 21.784 N, respectively. At 45° (diagonal direction), the cut forces increased to 11.71 N, 25.747 N, and 23.61 N. The highest cut resistance was observed at 90° (widthwise direction), with values of 16.279 N for 13U, 32.431 N for 13SU, and 26.128 N for 13GU (**Figure 10 k**). The data indicates that the highest cut resistant values at 90° in all samples, while minimum cut resistant values occur at 0° and intermediate at 45° .

Figure 10. (a-c) Schematic representation of different cutting directions in weft plain knitted structure. (d-f) Performing cut-test on 13SU fabrics at cutting angles of 0°, 45°, and 90°. (g-i) Optical images of knit loops fractures in 13SU fabric at these cutting angles. (j) Force-extension curve of the samples in lengthwise and widthwise directions. (k) Histogram of cutting load of the samples at 0°, 45°, and 90° cutting angles.

There are several factors contribute to these observations, primarily being the extensibility of samples in both the lengthwise and widthwise directions. As shown in Force - Extension graph in **Figure 10 j**, the extensibility of 13U, 13GU, and 13SU samples in widthwise direction (99.4 mm, 107.5 mm, 110.5 mm) was higher compared to lengthwise direction (58.7 mm, 61.6 mm, 72.3 mm) because, in weft knitted fabrics the loop structure is very flexible in course direction. So, in widthwise direction, when blade moves with constant speed on fabric surface in widthwise direction (**Figure 10 f**), the fabric absorbs the mechanical energy applied by cutting force more effectively. This is due to the maximum mobility of yarns in the direction of blade movement, as shown in **Figure 10 i**. This mobility leads to an unstable contact area between the blade edge and the loops, resulting in a loose grip. Consequently, the frictional force reduced, requiring higher shear force to generate cracks in the loops. This is because of the fabric's maximal elastic potential energy in widthwise direction, which contributes to its resistant to cutting forces. In contrast, fabric's lowest extensibility in lengthwise direction, when blade moves in this direction (at 0°) (**Figure 10 d**), limits this energy absorption, and results in a better contact area with tight gripping between blade edges and loops due to lesser mobility of yarns, as shown in **Figure 10 g**. This leads to a lower shear force being sufficient to cut through the loops. The 13SU fabric, which exhibits the maximum extensibility in both the widthwise and lengthwise directions compared to 13GU and 13U, shows the highest cut performance overall, that can absorb more energy before yielding to the cutting force, contributing to its superior cut resistance. On the other hand, the extensibility of 13GU is not as high as 13SU, primarily due to the brittle nature of the glass fibers, which makes the fabric more rigid and less capable of stretching to absorb energy. This rigidity results in lower cut resistance compared to 13SU.

3.3 Effect of environmental conditions

The cut-performance of 13SU, 13GU and 13U samples was investigated by exposing them in open environment for 90 days. After a time, span of 30 days, the mechanical properties of all fabric samples are measured and reported in **Figure 11 c-f**, **Supporting Figure S4**, and **Supporting Figure S5**. The results show a progressive decrease in these properties across all samples with extended exposure to the open environment over 30, 60, and 90 days. The most significant degradation in mechanical properties was observed in the 13SU fabric, followed by 13GU and then 13U, which is due to the galvanic corrosion in 13SU, where the stainless-steel

corrodes and generates oxidative byproducts that catalyse the oxidative degradation of the UHMWPE fibers, resulting in a more rapid breakdown of UHMWPE polymer chains and a subsequent decline in mechanical properties. Additionally, due to the high thermal conductivity of stainless-steel, it efficiently absorbs and distributes heat from sunlight throughout the structure. This increased heat exposure exacerbates the thermal degradation of UHMWPE fibers, leading to further damage. The FTIR spectra of 13SU (**Figure 11 b**) reveal significant changes in the chemical structure of UHMWPE fibers over time, particularly with the emergence of new peaks at 1708 cm^{-1} and 3432 cm^{-1} , corresponding to ketone (C=O) and hydroxyl (O-H) polar groups, respectively. The intensities of these peaks increase with prolonged exposure, indicating ongoing oxidative processes that introduce these functional groups into the UHMWPE chemical structures. Environmental factors such as oxygen and UV radiation initiate free radical formation, leading to polymer chain degradation and the formation of these functional groups. Concurrently, the fundamental bands of UHMWPE, such as the C-H stretching modes at 2851 cm^{-1} and 2919 cm^{-1} , the methylene bending vibration at 1462 cm^{-1} , and the CH_2 rocking mode at 719 cm^{-1} . Over a time, by exposing the samples in open environment, the intensities of these peaks decrease, suggesting a reduction in intact methylene groups and overall degradation of the polymer backbone, further supported by the consistent decrease in the intensity of these characteristic bands, reflecting the impact of environmental exposure on the material's chemical structures. The mechanical properties of 13SU fabric, exhibit a clear decline with increased environmental exposure, consistent with the FTIR findings. Tear strength in the widthwise direction decreases from 405.8 N (non-exposed) to 391 N (30 days), 365 N (60 days), and 310 N (90 days), while in the lengthwise direction, it drops from 313.1 N (non-exposed) to 305.6 N (30 days), 287.5 N (60 days), and 245.9 N (90 days) (**Figure 11 c**). Puncture resistance performance also decreases, with the puncture load dropping from 96.25 N (non-exposed) to 92.42 N (30 days), 85.68 N (60 days), and 74.57 N (90 days). Similarly, the number of cycles to hole formation in abrasion resistance tests declines from 800 cycles (non-exposed) to 780 cycles (30 days), 750 cycles (60 days), and 700 cycles (90 days) (**Figure 11 d**). The cutting load for a 20 mm corrected cut-through distance (CCTD) shows a reduction from 25.74 N (non-exposed) to 23.37 N (30 days), 20.81 N (60 days), and 17.09 N (90 days) (**Figure 11 f**). The correlation between the FTIR spectra and mechanical properties is evident. As the FTIR spectra show increased formation of ketone and hydroxyl groups (peaks at 1708 cm^{-1} and 3432 cm^{-1}), indicating oxidation, the mechanical properties degrade. These polar group into the UHMWPE polymer disrupt the non-polar nature of UHMWPE, reducing

its hydrophobicity and weakened intermolecular forces within the UHMWPE polymer, leading to chain scission and a decrease in molecular weight, reduces its mechanical strength.

Figure 11. (a) Outdoor environmental exposure of developed samples up to 90 days. (b) FTIR analysis of non-exposed and exposed 13SU sample. Effect of outdoor environmental exposure on 13SU: (c) breaking strength, (d) puncture and abrasion resistance, (e) the CCTD vs load

data and regression line curve (f) histogram of cutting load at 20-mm CCTD, derived from CCTD vs load curve.

3.4 Effect of radiant heat exposure

XRD curves of all exposed samples at heat flux density of 20 kW/m² on the mandrel of TDM-100, as shown in **Figures 12 a-b and Supporting Figure S6**, reveals that consistent decrease in peak intensities at 21.5° and 23.9° for all samples, indicating decreased crystallinity. This decline is attributed to thermal agitation, where increased kinetic energy disrupts the ordered arrangement of polymer chains, shifting the structure from crystalline to more amorphous. DSC analysis supports this observation, showing that UHMWPE, with a melting point (T_m) of approximately 141 °C, which is significantly lower than the T_m of 230 °C for polyester, indicating UHMWPE is very sensitive to thermal effects at lower temperatures (**Figure 12 c**). Among the fabrics, 13SU shows the most significant crystallinity loss, with an 11.72% reduction. This is likely due to the high thermal conductivity of stainless-steel fibers (approximately 13 to 15 W/m·K),⁴¹ which facilitate rapid heat transfer throughout the UHMWPE fibers, leading to elevated temperatures within the polymer structures. As the UHMWPE polymer chains are exposed to this heat, the increased molecular motion results in entropy-driven disorder, causing a breakdown of the crystalline regions. The disruption of these regions not only reduces crystallinity but also affects the overall crystal size and morphology. SEM images of 13SU (**Figure 12 e**) reveal extensive deformation and bead formation of UHMWPE fibers throughout the fabric, correlating with a substantial drop in cut resistance from 25.74 N to 18.76 N after exposure (**Figure 12 d**). While, 13GU shows better thermal stability, with only a 6.36 % reduction in crystallinity. The lower thermal conductivity of glass fibers as compared to stainless-steel fibers, helps insulate the UHMWPE fibers and minimizes the increase in entropy within the polymer, which helps in reducing the extent of degradation. SEM analysis shows only localized deformation of UHMWPE fibers and minimal structural damage in 13GU (**Figure 12 f**), consistent with a smaller decline in cut resistance from 23.6 N to 20.17 N, indicating its superior ability to maintain performance under thermal stress. The 13U fabric, composed solely of UHMWPE, shows an intermediate response, with a crystallinity reduction of about 9%. While it lacks the reinforcing fibers present in 13SU and 13GU, it still undergoes significant thermal agitation, leading to moderate degradation. SEM images of 13U (**Supporting Figure S7**) show some fiber dislocation, with a corresponding decrease in cut resistance, though less pronounced than in 13SU.

Figure 12. XRD curves of radiant heat exposed; (a) 13SU, and (b) 13GU samples. (c) DSC curves of UHMWPE/Polyester blend filaments. (d) The cutting load comparison of radiant heat

exposed and non-exposed 13SU, and 13GU samples at 20-mm CCTD. (e-f) The SEM images of radiant heat exposed 13SU, and 13GU samples.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, three types of knitted fabrics (in form of gloves) were prepared, including 100% UHMWPE (13U), stainless-steel reinforced UHMWPE (13SU), and glass-reinforced UHMWPE (13GU), using a 13-gauge gloves knitting machine. The study analysed the effect of reinforcing materials, radiant heat exposure, outdoor environmental conditions, and cutting angles on the durability and cut-resistance properties of developed samples. The findings revealed that reinforcement with stainless-steel and glass fibers significantly enhanced the mechanical (tear resistance, puncture resistance, and abrasion resistance) and cut-resistance properties. The 13SU fabric, reinforced with stainless steel, exhibited the highest overall performance under normal conditions, with an increased peak intensity and crystallinity percentage of 52.48% in its crystalline structure, compared to 13GU (51.75%) and 13U (48.37%), as confirmed by XRD graphs. This enhancement is attributed to the nucleating effect of stainless-steel, which promotes a more ordered alignment of UHMWPE polymer chains, leading to improved cut-resistance properties. However, this same reinforcement also contributed to the fabric more vulnerable to environmental degradation, particularly through galvanic corrosion and oxidative degradation, which resulted in formation of ketone (C=O) and hydroxyl (O-H) polar groups, that reduced the peak intensity and altered the molecular structure of UHMWPE polymer over time (up to 90 days), as confirmed by FTIR analyses.

Radiant heat exposure further impacted the crystallinity of the UHMWPE polymer, particularly in the 13SU sample, where the high thermal conductivity of stainless-steel facilitated rapid heat transfer, leading to a significant loss in crystallinity and molecular weight. In contrast, the 13GU fabric, reinforced with glass fibers, demonstrated better thermal stability due to the lower thermal conductivity of glass, which minimized the degradation of UHMWPE's molecular structure and preserved its mechanical and cut performance. The study also found that cut resistance for all samples was highest at 90° (widthwise direction) and lowest at 0° (lengthwise direction), influenced by the fabric's extensibility, which was higher in the widthwise direction compared to the lengthwise direction. This increased extensibility allowed the fabric to absorb more energy through the loops and polymer structure, thereby contributing to its superior cut resistance at 90° cutting angle.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

- 1) The detailed information about the effect of outdoor environmental exposure on 13GU and 13U sample along with XRD curves, and SEM images of radiant heat exposed 13U sample.

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